

Effect of Filled Potassium Titanate Whiskers on the Processability and the Mechanical Properties of Plastic Composites

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ABSTRACT

In the composite materials composed of potassium titanate whiskers (PTW) as filler and plastics, such as polyacetal (POM), polybutyleneterephthalate (PBT) and epoxy resin (EP), the effect of the filler content on the processability and on the mechanical properties of moldings were experimentally studied, as compared with those of the composites filled with glass fibers (GF). The processing characteristics of the PTW filled composites, such as fluidity in melt and molding shrinkage, were more excellent than those of GF filled composites. The mechanical properties, such as tensile, compressive and impact strength, of PTW filled composites were larger than those of the GF filled composites because the adhesive strength between matrix and PTW, which was estimated by the contact angle between them, was to be greater than that between matrix and GF, while the aspect ratio of PTW was much smaller than that of GF.

INTRODUCTION

In this study, the plastic composite materials filled with potassium titanate whiskers (PTW) were experimentally surveyed on those processability and mechanical properties of injection or compression moldings, as compared with those filled with glass fibers (GF). When fine PTW, that is, 1/400 of a cross-sectional area and 1/100 in length compared with glass fiber, is used for a filler to make the composites, the allowable limit of filler content in the molding process, the flow property of molten composites, mold shrinkage and the effect of coupling agents on the adhesive property or the contact angle between the matrix and filler were studied. And these experiments also attempted to discover the influence on the mechanical strengths, such as tensile, flexural, compressive, impact and hardness, by the PTW content and the treatment with the coupling agent in regard to the composites made from polyacetal (or polyoxymethylene POM), polybutylene terephthalate (PBT) and epoxy resin (EP) as the matrix and PTW as filler.

EXPERIMENT AND RESULTS

1). Matrix, Filler and Coupling Agent

Table 1 shows the characteristics of PTW used as fillers in the experiments. The coupling agents employed to improve the adhesiveness were chosen from a

group of Silan consisting of A-1100, A-172 or A-187 made by the Union Carbide Co., or the Titanate coupling agents of KEN-REACT, TTS, 9S, 38S or 138S. The matrix tested were POM (copolymerized, Duracon), PBT (Duranex) and epoxy resin (Epicoat-828).

2) Effect of Coupling Agent

Fig. 1 shows the contact angle θ at several different temperatures between the liquid epoxy resin and the PTW plate surface treated with each Silan coupling agent. Treated plates have less θ than untreated one, and the A-1100-treated one shows the least value of θ . Fig. 2 shows the contact angle at 140 °C between the epoxy resin and the glass or the PTW plate treated with the Silan coupling agent. Generally speaking, the contact angle of PTW was considerably smaller than that of the glass plate, which proves the high adhesiveness of treated PTW. Fig. 3 also demonstrates the contact angle between the PBT or POM and glass or PTW plate treated by various coupling agents at each predetermined temperature. And similar tendency to Fig. 2 also was observed in the Figure.

3). Viscosity of Molten Composites and Mold Shrinkage

Fig. 4 shows the relationship of the coefficient of viscosity measured by a rheometer and the temperature for the composites containing 5, 15 and 30 % glassfiber or PTW in polypropylene (PP) and unfilled PP. In general, the composites filled with PTW had less and easier fluidity than that filled with

Table 1 Characteristics of PTW

Properties	TISMO - D
Colour and State	White, Needle crystal
Chemical composition	$K_2O \cdot 6TiO_2$
Specific weight	3.1 - 3.3
Mean diameter	0.2 - 0.5 μm
Mean length	2.0 - 3.0 μm
Melting temp.	1300 - 1500 °C
Tensile strength	7000 MPa
Tensile modulus	280000 MPa

Fig.1 Relations between contact angle θ and temperature τ for the various surface treatments by coupling agents

Fig. 2 Contact angle between epoxy resin and each filler, PTW or GF plate, for various surface treatments by each Silan coupling agent (140 °C)

glass fibers (GF). Table 2 illustrates the each mold shrinkage rate for the flow direction or the transverse direction to flow. The materials tested were unfilled PBT, 30% filled PTW or GF in PBT by the same injection mold. The composites filled with PTW had slightly less shrinkage and directional difference T/F than that filled with GF. The maximum filling rate of PTW was about 23% in epoxy resin and about 30% in POM or PBT.

4) Modulus of Elasticity, Tesile and Flexural Strength

Fig. 5 shows the relationship between the tensile modulus of elasticity E_T and the filler content of PTW or GF in PBT at various coupling agents. The figure shows that the composites filled with PTW had about 30% larger value of E than that filled with GF.

Fig. 6 shows the relationship between the tensile strength and the filler content of the composites. The tensile strength increases direct-proportionally to the filler content and is in the range of 57-90 MPa, and the PTW filled one holds around a 20% higher than the GF-filled one. The data of the tensile strength σ_c , flexural strength σ_f , modulus of flexural elasticity E_b , and the value of Izod impact strength U_i is summarized in Fig.7 for PBT composites that were filled at a 30% ratio with PTW treated by 0-2% of the coupling agent A-1100, and the optimum application rate is found to be at 1%.

Fig.8 shows the relationship between the values of σ_c , σ_b , E_b , U_i and the content of PTW treated by A-1100, and it is clear that the values of σ_c and σ_b filled at 30% PTW increase almost two times of those of unfilled PBT. The shearing adhesive strength ζ between PTW and PBT can be estimated from the equation (2), using the critical length of $l_c = 0.03$ mm calculated from the law of composite equation (1). The result shows a rather high performance of 41 MPa, in other words, PTW and Pbt adhere to each other tightly.

$$\sigma_{ci} = \frac{1}{2} \sigma_f \left(1 - \frac{l_c}{2l}\right) V_f + \sigma_{bi} (1 - V_f) \dots\dots\dots(1)'$$

$$l_c = \frac{\sigma_f d}{2 \tau_f} \dots\dots\dots(2)'$$

where σ_c is the tensile strength of the composites, σ_f (tensile strength of filler) = 5000 MP, d (diameter of filler) = 0.0005 mm, l (length of filler) = 0.02 mm, V_f (volume content of fillers), σ_{ci} (actual tensile strength of composites) = 112 MPa,

Fig. 3 Contact angle θ between PBT or POM and GF or PTW plate treated by various Silan or Titanate coupling agents

Fig. 4 Relation between the coefficient of viscosity η and the temperature for PP composites containing each percentage of PTW or GF

Table 2 Mold shrinkage of PBT composites

Filler content (wt %)	Shrinkage (%)		T / F
	Direction		
	Flow (F)	Transverse (T)	
0	2.7	3.4	1.2.5
PTW - 3.0	0.8	2.6	3.2
GF - 3.0	0.7	2.9	4.1

Fig. 5 Relation between the tensile modulus of elasticity E_t and the filler content of PTW or GF at various coupling levels

Fig. 6 Relations between the tensile strength and the filler content in POM composites for each surface treatment

Fig. 7 Relations between σ_x , σ_b , E_t , U_i and the density of coupling agent, A-1100, for PBT composites filled with PTW of 30%

Fig. 8 Relations between σ_x , σ_b , E_t , U_i and the content of PTW for PBT composites

(tensile stress of the matrix at the breaking elongation of the filler) = 25 MPa.

5) Compressive and Impact Strength and Hardness

Fig. 9 illustrates the compressive strength of epoxy resin filled with 20% of PTW treated by various coupling agents. The figure reveals composites increase to around 200 MPa compressive strength from 130 MPa of unfilled

Fig. 9 Compressive strength of epoxy resin composites filled with PTW of 20% for each surface treatment by various coupling agents

Fig. 10 Relation between compressive strength and the content of filler in POM for each surface treatment or mixing method

resin. A comparison of the compressive strength and the filler content of the composites is shown in Fig. 10, when they are made from POM filled with PTW or GF. The compressive strength ascends to around 20% higher for the composites filled with PTW, and descends to around 15% lower for the GF-filled one.

Fig. 11 shows the Izod impact strength U_i versus the filler content of the composites made from epoxy resin and PTW as a filler treated by various coupling agents. The strength using untreated PTW is nearly constant at any filler content, but it increases as the rate goes up.

Fig. 12 shows the relationship of the surface hardness H_v (Vickers hardness) and the filler content in POM composites filled with PTW and GF treated by various coupling agents. The hardness in the range of 14.3-21 increases proportionally to the filler content, and the composites filled with PTW have a

Fig. 11 Relation between Izod impact strength and the PTW content in epoxy resin for each surface treatment

Fig. 12 Relation between Vickers hardness H and the content of filler in POM for each surface treatment or mixing method

higher value than with GF.

CONCLUSION

- 1) The maximum filler content exist at 20% for epoxy resin and 30% for POM or PBT, when PTW is mixed with a plastics to produce a composites materials.
- 2) The composites filled with PTW shows better fluidity and mold shrinkage deviation of the flow axis vs the transverse than the GF-filled one.
- 3) The contact angle between the resin and PTW is smaller than that of glass. Therefore a higher adhesiveness is achieved by PTW.
- 4) The law of composites can be applied for tensile and flexural strength of composites made from PTW and plastics. Average shearing adhesive strength between PTW and plastics achieves a value as high as about 41 MP .
- 5) The compressive and impact strength of composites will generally go down for a short-GF-filled one. On the contrary, it increases for the PTW-filled one.

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